

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
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- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
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Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

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Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

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THE CONTRIBUTION OF ECOTOURISM IN DEVELOPING GDP IN UZBEKISTAN

Saidova Dildora Nurmatovna

PhD of Economic Sciences, Tashkent State Agrarian University,
Uzbekistan

Umarov Husanboy Bahromjon o'g'li

2nd-grade student, Tashkent State Agrarian University, Uzbekistan

Holyigitov Umidjon Alijon o'g'li

1st year students, Tashkent State Agrarian University, Uzbekistan

Abstract: Ecotourism has become a major tool for the rising environmental awareness of locals and visitors ensuring long-term sustainability. The tourists are becoming increasingly sophisticated in having meaningful travel experiences including communication with local people, learning their culture, observation of unique ecosystems, flora and fauna of the untouched areas. Uzbekistan's diverse ecology from mountains to deserts, from deserts to plains can support the country with the great ecotourism potential. Such opportunities can provide social, environmental and economic benefits to the country when it is comprehensively modified and meets international standards.

Key words: Ecotourism, nature, environmental impact, sustainability, conservation awareness, reserves, fauna, flora, Global warming, GDP, tourism, Contribution of tourism, summit, tourism industry, ecological catastrophe.

Annotatsiya: Ekoturizm uzoq muddatli barqarorlikni ta'minlovchi mahalliy aholi va tashrif buyuruvchilarning ekologik xabardorligini oshirishning asosiy vositasiga aylandi. Sayyohlar mazmunli sayohat tajribasiga ega bo'lish, jumladan, mahalliy aholi bilan muloqot qilish, ularning madaniyatini o'rganish, noyob ekotizimlar, tabiiy hududlarning o'simlik va faunasini kuzatishda tobora qiziqmoqda. O'zbekistonning tog'lardan cho'lgacha, cho'ldan tekislikgacha bo'lgan xilma-xil ekologiyasi katta ekoturizm salohiyatiga ega. Bunday imkoniyatlar har tomonlama rivojlantirilishi va xalqaro standartlarga javob berishi mamlakatga ijtimoiy, ekologik va iqtisodiy foyda keltirishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: Ekoturizm, tabiat, atrof-muhitga ta'siri, barqarorlik, tabiatni muhofaza qilish, qo'riqxonalar, fauna, flora, Global isish, YaIM, turizm, Turizm hissasi, sammit, turizm sanoati, ekologik halokat.

Аннотация: Экотуризм, обеспечивая долгосрочную устойчивость страны, является инструментом повышения экологической осведомленности местных жителей и гостей. Туристы, общаясь с местным населением, изучают их культуру, наблюдая за уникальными экосистемами, флорой и фауной территорий, получают содержательный опыт от путешествий. Разнообразная экология Узбекистана, от гор до пустынь, от пустынь до равнин, может принести выгоду стране с огромным потенциалом экотуризма. Такие социальные, экологические и экономические выгоды дадут возможность роста ВВП страны, если использовать потенциал экотуризма, всесторонне будет соответствовать международным стандартам.

Ключевые слова: экотуризм, природа, воздействие на окружающую среду, устойчивость, осведомленность об охране природы, заповедники, фауна, флора, глобальное потепление, ВВП, туризм, экологическая катастрофа.

INTRODUCTION

Currently we have a massive responsibility for helping to raise the contribution of tourism in GDP. One of our most important duties is to solve the issues that are being barriers to bring forth a totally new atmosphere and page in Tourism. I think one of the most powerful clues is increasing the quality and the level of services. A couple weeks ago the biggest summit came up in Samarkand and it involved the entire tourism industry through the developed countries. It was the hugest phenomena throughout the years. This helped our tourism industry to show up its strength and the true power. In this ceremony we gained a lot of experience which can lead our tourism industry to rise up.

DATA AND METHODS

In the process of research, theoretical methods of induction, deduction, generalization and comparison were used. The necessary materials are investigated on the basis of the methods of typological analysis, the synthesis of statistical data

MAIN RESULTS

In this year, we pulled up around 1.7 milliard dollars out of 80 milliard dollars which is the rate of our Gross domestic product. As a result, it helped to move the rate of our tourism contribution in GDP forward, that's to say the contribution of tourism industry has showed up it's upward trend by changing it's percentage from 1,7 to 2,5 percentage and that is our advantage to hit 5 percent in GDP by amplifying the number and quality of services.

Despite having potential, income from tourism in Uzbekistan does not exceed 2 percent of GDP, whereas in other countries (Spain, the United States, France, Egypt, Malaysia, the U. A.E.) tourism revenues range from 10 to 45% of GDP.

However, services are the most essential chain of tourism. Because it can hold tourism and GDP together. I believe that, if we make deals with other well developed countries in terms of tourism and services we will be able to raise the percentage of tourism in the upcoming years and it will have a proper effect on our economy and the quality of our lives as well.

More than 50 percent of the population lives in urbanized areas. Uzbekistan is the world's fifth-largest exporter and seventh-largest producer of cotton, but unsound cultivation has degraded the land and depleted water supplies. The economy also relies on exports of natural gas and gold.

Second of all, the factor that has a sharp influence after services on the contribution of tourism is the number of tour packages. The fact that tour packages are important is because there are no other ways of traveling all over the world without any packages that are specifically created for tourists who have a huge passion about traveling through the countries officially.

In 2021 Uzbekistan ranked 16th out of 140 countries in the Global Muslim Travel Index. In 2022 the government updated its plans and set the goal to increase the number of foreign tourists to 9 million and domestic tourists to 12 million, and to invest \$300 million in creation of tourism and recreation zones by 2026. Uzbekistan can enhance its tourism potential by strengthening its cooperation with other countries and international organizations. Additionally, Uzbekistan should explore its cultural and natural attractions, and invest in advertising to raise awareness about these sites. Because, marketing is the most viral clue to open the world of tourism. In contrast, if we don't have any believable advertisement about everything we have in Uzbekistan like its historical places and buildings, admirable beauty of nature and landscape, modernable places. That's to say our government has to make them believe our advertisement in order to stock up the first compression in tourist's minds. Our main duty is bringing forth a totally new unexpected atmosphere that they don't even think about. Not only advertisement but also the design of the website should be much more attractive and competitive than other usual websites. We have to provide international tourists with full information about traveling, staying in the hotels and their prices, types, national and international foods, attractions, health insurance and of course profits. Because those all will be taken into consideration while choosing an exceptional country to travel with a bunch of advantages and unforgettable memories. It alleviates them not to feel strange, insecure or unvalidated in a totally different country, region, citizen and culture. Tourism generates income for a variety of businesses and creates a wide range of employment opportunities. At the global scale, tourism is seen as one of the world's largest and fastest growing industries. On October 5, Tashkent hosted the international conference "Eco-tourism – an important factor in sustainable development and environmental protection: the experience of Uzbekistan and foreign practice". The forum is organized by the State Committee for Nature Protection in cooperation with the National Company "Uzbektourism" with the participation of the OSCE Project Coordinator in Uzbekistan. The conference has been attended by representatives of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, ministries, departments and public organizations, international agencies – UNWTO, UNEP, UNECE, major financial institutions, the diplomatic corps, experts, domestic and foreign media.

An executive director for technical cooperation and services of the World Tourism Organization Shanchzhong Zhu has become an honorable guest of the forum. Speaking at the opening ceremony, he said that Uzbekistan is one of the most dynamically developing countries and an important partner of the UNWTO. In recent years, eco-tourism has become a segment of tourism and a new area in the tourism industry. The resolutions of the UN General Assembly from 2012 and 2014 recognize the importance of the development of eco-tourism in order to preserve natural resources and international cooperation in this field. It is emphasized that the holding

of this conference is very timely, and considered questions are relevant not only for Uzbekistan but also for the whole world, especially in light of the fact that the United Nations has proclaimed 2017th year as the International Year of Sustainable Tourism for Development. As known, our country has great prospects for the development of eco-tourism, establishing a unique and sustainable network of ecotourism routes with the further integration of the republic into the international market such services which are attractive for all categories of tourists. Today Uzbekistan is one of the leading places in Central Asia by popular ecotourism destinations. Conference was opened by a video show, dedicated to the natural and biological diversity of Uzbekistan and its ecotourism potential.

In order to boost ecotourism's potential I have already tried to make a perfect project that helps to figure out the weaknesses and threats. One of them is created specially for children. The core of this project was helping the young generation to acclimatize to the new atmosphere which is called Ecotourism and as it planned we wanted to perform their basic knowledge and skills. This is like a platform that gives daily tasks which are useful to improve their brain process and their life faith. After a week of progress that we have been waiting for a long time, they are changing their mind to belong to nature and respect and be kind to the worlds of flora and fauna which are the core items of life time.

In 2021, Uzbekistan generated around 679.00 million US dollars in the tourism sector alone. This corresponds to 0.84 percent of its gross domestic product and approximately 39 percent of all international tourism receipts in Central Asia. The development of ecotourism in Uzbekistan is based on its spirituality, science, culture, enlightenment, nature protection, increasing the interest of ecotourists in our native nature, conservation of rare flora and fauna and solving the problems of endangered flora and fauna. Uzbekistan's exports of tourism services reached \$1.6 billion in 2022 and its targets for 2024 are 7 million foreign tourists and \$2.5 billion in tourism exports. Ecotourism is widely regarded as an effective strategy for many nations, as it helps to preserve natural areas, safeguard cultural traditions, generate revenue for national development, and employ locals. Ecotourism, which primarily serves conservation interests, helps promote ecologically sound growth. The tourism opportunities of our country are very diverse and rich: these are Ugam-Chatkal National Park, and the forests in the Amu Darya River Delta, the Kitab Nature Reserve, recently opened for tourists, testifying to the appearance of life on our planet, the region of the "ecological catastrophe" near the boundary countries.

CONCLUSION

Ecotourism in Uzbekistan is rooted in its spiritual, scientific, cultural and educational values, as well as its commitment to protect nature, increase the curiosity of ecotourists in our native landscapes, preserve the diversity of plants and animals and address the issues of threatened species. Research indicates that tourism is a vital source of foreign currency for Uzbekistan and other countries, it boosts the growth of trade and other sectors of the economy, as well as the agricultural industry, and creates jobs for the people. Ecotourism is widely seen as a beneficial approach for many nations, as it helps to maintain natural areas, protect cultural heritage, generate income for national development, and employ local people. Ecotourism, which mainly serves conservation goals, helps foster environmentally friendly development. It can directly benefit local communities through the development of infrastructure such as better roads and lodging. This can make it easier for locals to access essential services and make it more likely that tourists will return to the area in the future. The total income of the population of Uzbekistan was 338.4 trillion sums in the first half of 2023. It rose by 6.5% in real terms compared to the same period last year. Per capita income was 9.3 million sums and increased by 4.3% in real terms.

The development of transport infrastructure also plays an important role in attracting tourists. Uzbekistan is actively upgrading its aviation, railway and road systems. Renovation of international airports in Tashkent, Samarkand and Bukhara, contributes to higher passenger traffic and better services. Extensive plains covered by various types of deserts, mountain steppes, mountain forests and alpine meadows, riparian woodland forests in the desert river valleys, wetlands, and oases represent different ecosystems with their distinctive plant and animal communities. Generally speaking it is defined as responsible travel to natural areas that conserves the environment and improves the well-being of local people

All in all, We have to admit that reciprocity between us and nature in terms of friendship is not getting on well with its qualities at all. Our duty is to figure out all the privileges which can be on our side to alleviate the situation that is about to come up in the nearest years. People shouldn't not only just predict the events but also not leave nature on their own or just watch out how nature is suffering from factors that we are creating and being the ringleader for this. Stop making this and save the world for the younger generation.

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Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

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